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ABSTRACTS

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Genome mining for bacterial biosynthetic clusters with antimicrobial potential

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Abstract: Bacteria synthesize a wide array of secondary metabolites with properties including antimicrobial activity, metal sequestration, antioxidants, and chemo/osmoprotectants, which are of biotechnological and pharmaceutical interest. The aim of the present study was the mining of secondary metabolite biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) from bacterial strains phylogenetically identified as *Serratia* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Paenibacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., and *Priestia* sp. that were isolated from drain sludge. Whole genome analysis identified the biosynthesis clusters belonging to non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (NRPS) type (prodigiosin, paenibacterin, polymyxin, ectoine), metallophores (yersinopine, bacillopaline) and siderophores (bacillibactin, ochrobactin). Further analysis revealed that the isolated bacteria harbor an array of candidate novel BGCs for synthesis of bioactive molecules. Some of the secondary metabolites, namely prodigiosin, paenibacterin, polymyxin, and bacitracin, have been reported for their antimicrobial activity. The study provided genomic insights into the production of diverse antimicrobial compounds by the isolated strains. Further characterization of the novel clusters will provide the genetic foundation for upscaling secondary metabolite synthesis for biotechnological applications.

Keywords: Genome mining, secondary metabolites, BGCs, antimicrobial activity.

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